

**LISTENING TO AN ALPINE INTERMITTENT
STREAM: DEVELOPMENT OF AN
AUTONOMOUS MICROCONTROLLER DEVICE
TO MEASURE WATER LEVEL**

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Abstract

Intermittent rivers and ephemeral streams (IRES) account for 50% of the world's flows. Climate change leads to an increase in intermittent streams from perennial streams. Recently, IRES have been found to be very important for carbon and nitrogen cycling and ecosystem functions. Despite recent attention towards IRES, spatial and temporal data lack, especially in mountain areas. Conventional measuring techniques depend on devices that have certain limitations, for example, they are placed in the streambed, where they get destroyed or displaced during a heavy stream flow event. This thesis presents a self-developed, low-cost audio sensor that can derive the water level of an IRES using only sound. In addition to an audio sensor, a time-lapse camera constantly documented the streambed and captured the water level at thirty-minute intervals. The water level determined from the images and the audio files is strongly correlated with a 95% coefficient of determination (R^2). We can calculate the water level using the audio data with the exponential regression function, as long as there is some water in the stream. This work demonstrates the possibility of an audio sensor to obtain reliable water level data in an IRES and offers a legitimate alternative to conventional measuring methods. This technological advance offers a new affordable, accessible tool that can be widely used and thus increase monitoring of the flow of IRES at a large scale.

Free online access

The thesis with the relevant codes for Teensyduino, Processing and Matlab is open-sourced and accessible online on Zenodo.

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Contents

List of Figures	VII
List of Tables	VIII
List of Abbreviations	IX
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Role of IRES	1
1.2 Microcontroller	2
1.3 Sound of IRES	3
1.4 Goal of the master thesis	4
2 Methods	5
2.1 Data acquisition	5
2.1.1 Audio sensor	5
2.1.2 Image sensor	15
2.2 Field test	15
2.2.1 Field site	15
2.2.2 Mounting setup of sensor	18
2.3 Data evaluation	18
2.3.1 Sound processing	18
2.3.2 Image processing	19
2.3.3 Audio and image relationship	21
2.3.4 Supplementary data for validation	22
3 Results	25
3.1 Data acquisition	25
3.1.1 Audio sensor	25
3.1.2 Image sensor	26
3.2 Field test	26
3.2.1 Field site	26
3.2.2 Mounting setup	26
3.3 Data evaluation	26
3.3.1 Sound processing	26
3.3.2 Audio and image relationship	28

4	Discussion	34
4.1	Data acquisition	34
4.1.1	Audio sensor	34
4.2	Field test	35
4.2.1	Field site	35
4.2.2	Mounting setup	36
4.3	Data evaluation	36
4.3.1	Sound processing	36
4.3.2	Image processing	37
4.4	Audio and image relationship	38
4.4.1	Relationship of water level and SPL	38
4.4.2	Off points	39
4.4.3	Calibration	40
4.5	Limitation	40
4.6	Outlook	41
5	Conclusion	43
	Literatur	vi
6	Appendix	vii

List of Figures

1	Illustrations of how sound is created in a liquid medium	4
2	Block schematic of audio sensor	6
3	Teensy 3.2 (PJCR, 2022b)	7
4	Audio Shield from Teensy (PJRC, 2022)	8
5	Signal over time and frequency (NTI Audio, 2022)	9
6	Flowchart of program code from the audio sensor	12
7	Open audio sensor case	14
8	Valley of Nant	15
9	Potential ephemeral streams: southeast in the valley	16
10	Location of Sensor and Catchment Area of La Tsabou (0.60 km ²)	17
11	Sensor board mounted at the tree in the field site	18
12	Reference depth gauge	20
13	Virtual scale on image	20
14	Virtual scale	20
15	Virtual scale on time-lapse image	20
16	Precipitation of the four closest meteorological stations from MeteoSwiss and SensorScope	23
17	All 12 sound files of 2022-07-29 with every frequency bandwidth	27
18	Rain in comparison to no stream flow and stream flow in [SPL db]	28
19	2 Outliers	29
20	Every frequency bandwidth and its R^2	30
21	R^2 of all 19 frequency bandwidths	30
22	Audio files are included in the correlation function of water level and sound	31
23	2 Diagrams of correlation of water level and SPL and the calculated water level with precipitation	32
24	Number of stream flow events for accurate prediction of water level with audio	33
25	Snow packs above potential IRES in Valley of Nant	36
26	Correlation of image and sound of 0.05-1 kHz with σ of water level	37
27	Correlation of image and sound of 0.05-1 kHz	38
28	Off points are marked in the orange boxes	40
29	Frequency response of microphone (Projects Unlimited Inc., 2006)	viii
30	Location of meteorological stations around the sensor	viii

List of Tables

1	Current consumption in the different software modes. (Measurement with multimeter)	13
2	Closest precipitation meteorological stations from sensor site	22
3	Information about each stream flow event	24
4	Table of error events	25
5	Cost of each audio sensor part	vii
6	Applied exponential function: $f(x) = a \cdot \exp(b \cdot x)$	ix

List of Abbreviations

asl	Above sea level
CHF	Swiss francs
dB	Decibel
DC	Direct current
DFT	Discrete fourier transformation
DSP	Digital sound processing
FFT	Fast fourier transformation
Hz	Hertz
IDE	Integrated development environment
IRES	Intermittent rivers and ephemeral streams
kHz	Kilohertz
LED	light-emitting diodes
LiPo	Lithium polymer battery
mA	Milliamperere
mAh	Milliampererehour
PCM	Pulse-Code-Modulation
PJCR	Paul J Stoffregen and Robin C Coon
ppm	Particles per million
RTC	Real time clock
SoX	Sound eXchange
SPL	Sound pressure level
V	Volt
WAV	Waveform audio file format

1 Introduction

Half of all rivers and streams are intermittent or ephemeral (IRES) around the world (Datry et al., 2014). In mountainous regions, most of the rivers are intermittent (Benstead & Leigh, 2012). Due to climate change and the expected change in the annual distribution of precipitation, perennial streams increasingly become intermittent rivers (Leigh et al., 2016; Gobiet et al., 2014). In addition, change in land use impact the flow regime in IRES. Deforestation and the resulting loss of the possible water infiltration, for example, leads to a bigger surface runoff in the catchment area (Sajikumar & Remya, 2015). The amount of water in IRES changes constantly and leads to continuous changes in the water level and thus the conditions for fauna and flora alongside IRES (Datry et al., 2011). Despite the large number of IRES, there is a lack of spatial and temporal data to study the impact of IRES on fauna and flora (Stubbington et al., 2018; Costigan et al., 2017). Current IRES research determines the presence of water or the water level with sensors like electric conductivity, flow-switch, pressure transducers, temperature sensors, or time-lapse imagery (Assendelft & Ilja van Meerveld, 2019; Hinrich Kaplan et al., 2019; Penna et al., 2015). The unsteady water level of IRES makes it challenging to install sensors directly in the waterbed, which is a problem with the previously used measuring methods. Unlike installation in a stream bed, measurement methods from a distance are protected from the harsh conditions of IRES. From a distance, one can work with visual recognition of water or the emerging sound of flowing water. For example, Osborne et al. (2021) determined the water level with recordings of the flowing water in England. This thesis presents a water level determination method with the sound of IRES. Unlike Osborne et al. (2021), the study site for this thesis is at an IRES in a mountainous region, since the majority of streams in mountainous regions are intermittent. The lack of data in time and space motivated me to develop a cost-efficient sensor. Therefore the recording of IRES is conducted with a self-developed audio sensor with a microcontroller. The advantage of a cost-efficient and the self-developed sensor is the reproducibility of the device. Thereby it represents a solution to collect data in space and time of IRES.

1.1 Role of IRES

Unique of IRES is its partial stream flow, where the stream rises and ceases periodically (Datry et al., 2017; Larned et al., 2010; Introna et al., 2015). Stream flow in IRES can occur on different sources (Costigan et al., 2017; Datry et al., 2014; Introna et al., 2015). Since the groundwater level is below that of the river, the groundwater level does not provide any discharge. The first reason for discharge is snowmelt, which causes surface runoff and leads to stream flow. However, snow melting does not result in year-round runoff. Second, a spring can provide the stream with little water at times. Third, rainfall event causes a direct reaction in stream flow behavior. The mentioned reasons for discharge can lead to stream flow alone or in combination (Paillex et al.,

2020). The changing flow regime impacts the form of stream beds of IRES. Mainly stream beds of IRES are characterized by boulders and bed grains and do not provide a laminar flow (NC Division of Water Quality, 2005). The many roughness elements cause water deflection in the stream bed (Bathurst, 2002).

The variability of the flow regime has a significant impact on the biogeochemical processes and biota (Leigh et al., 2016; Costigan et al., 2017). Changing conditions of wet and dry periods help maintain biodiversity and stimulate biochemical cycles important for groundwater (Leigh et al., 2016). IRES create an interaction for carbon and nitrogen cycles zone between groundwater and stream water (Costigan et al., 2017). IRES also play an essential role in microbial diversity. Even under the harsh conditions of IRES, prokaryotes, fungi, and protozoans satisfy an important component in the nutrient exchange network (von Schiller et al., 2017). The constantly changing conditions lead to waves of microbial functions, which serve as a nutrient source for higher trophic levels (Romaní et al., 2017).

In recent years, IRES have become an emerging research topic (Leigh et al., 2016; Stubbington et al., 2018). However, IRES remain a complex field of study due to altering chemical, geomorphological, and hydrological processes (Leigh et al., 2016; Stubbington et al., 2018). Research about IRES needs a more acceptable resolution of spatiotemporal data of IRES to get an in-depth knowledge of IRES (Stubbington et al., 2018; Costigan et al., 2017). For example in Valley of Nant, Mächler et al. (2021) needed to make approximations for the discharge of ephemeral and tributary streams. Furthermore, researchers stress the importance of more research on flow regime (Michelon et al., 2021; Fovet et al., 2021). Fovet et al. (2021) emphasize the need for water level measurement stations to characterize the hydrological regime of IRES. But low flows and discharge stops are still challenging to measure with acceptable accuracy, due to the constantly changing sizes in the stream bed (Fovet et al., 2021). The water level can be used to calculate the discharge with a rating curve. Still, the unsteady flow regime causes uncertainty in low flows calculation (Freestone, 1983).

1.2 Microcontroller

In the future, microcontrollers can collect data in higher resolution of space and time. In particular, microcontrollers as a datalogger are a cost-effective alternative to common measuring devices (Assendelft & Ilja van Meerveld, 2019; Bhamjee & Lindsay, 2011). At low acquisition cost, various sensors can be built and developed to generate the desired data resolution. An advantage of self-developed software for microcontroller datalogger is to adapt the code to the need of the scientific question. The same applies to the hardware; a better understanding of the installed technology of the data logger is given and guarantees its reliability. Self-developed dataloggers with temperature sensors, electric conductivity, and flow-switch were used to determine the presence of water and its water level. The self-developed dataloggers have proven reliable ((Assendelft & Ilja

van Meerveld, 2019; Bhamjee & Lindsay, 2011). Nevertheless, conventional measuring techniques are limited. They are installed directly in the stream bed, so water, little rocks, boulders, and sediments are carried during a heavy flow event. Measuring devices can be destroyed or displaced. Time-lapse imagery provides an alternative because the sensor's device does not come into contact with the stream. Still, it is limited to daytime hours. However, the approach of time-lapse imagery, measuring from a distance, has not remained the only remote measuring technique for stream flow. Osborne et al. (2021) monitored streams in England with microphones and derived the water level from the sounds of the streams. In Hydrology, the idea to measure with a microphone of Osborne et al. (2021) is not unique. Many researchers are using sound for their research. For example, Hut (2013) recorded the amount of rainfall and the size of raindrops with a piezo microphone. Another application of microphones is the determination of bedload and sediment transport. The researchers took underwater audio recordings and drew conclusions about bedload transport (Thorne & Hanes, 2002; Nicollier et al., 2022). Since the audio signal is constant, it provides a high temporal resolution (Thorne & Hanes, 2002). Even in the world of flora, plants take an acoustic approach. Plants search for water in the soil with their roots. In the process, the plants use an acoustic procedure to detect the moist areas (Gagliano et al., 2017). Listening to river, as Osborne et al. (2021) did was the inspiration for this master thesis. The river monitoring was transformed into the alpine region and IRES.

1.3 Sound of IRES

The cause of water noise from IRES is complex. One of the first findings had Bragg (1919). His book *The World of Sounds* mentions that cavities are created by drops hitting the water's surface. These cavities are the reason for the sound of water. A drop falling (figure 1 illustration 1) into the water first creates an indentation (figure 1 illustration 2) in the surface before the water shoots up again. This finding is not the only cause. The actual impact of water drops on the water surface is relatively quiet. Instead, the bubbles created by the inundation (figure 1 illustration 3) make much more noise (Phillips et al., 2018).

In general, sound is a pressure wave. Vibrating objects create pressure waves. In a river, the oscillating air bubble operates as a vibrating object. The medium in which the pressure wave propagates can be air, liquid, or solid objects. The type of medium influences the speed of propagation of the wave. When a sound wave arrives at a human's eardrum, the pressure wave converts into an electrical signal transmitted to the brain. The brain perceives it as sound (The Physics Classroom, 2016b,a). One of the characteristics of sound is the wavelength. The wavelength is the distance a wave propagates until it repeats itself. The number of repeated cycles of wavelengths in a second is called frequency. Its measurement unit is hertz (Hz) (Goyal, 2018).

The process of sound in a liquid medium can be experienced every day. Water is poured into a glass, and the sound from the pouring is audible. The sound becomes louder when more water is

Figure 1: *Illustrations of how sound is created in a liquid medium*

1: Water drop falls

2: Inundation on the water surface and creates a cavity

3: Oscillating bubble below water surface

poured at once. The rapid rebound of the water creates a small air bubble directly underneath the indentation. Also, the faster the poured water drops on the surface, the more extensive turbulence and air bubbles are created. In IRES, water deflects and collides with rigid elements, creating turbulence in the water. The bubbles oscillate in the turbulent stream. The equation to calculate the frequencies produced by the bubble considers the radius of the bubble (Minnaert, 1933). Tiny bubbles create high-pitched sounds, whereas more giant bubbles create low-pitched sounds (Leighton, 1994).

1.4 Goal of the master thesis

The need for spatial and temporal data and the possibility of self-developed data loggers were fundamental to the goal of the master thesis. Inspiring was the work of Osborne et al. (2021) as a measurement technique with sound. Hence, I wanted to develop an audio sensor to record sounds from IRES in a mountainous region. In addition to the audio sensor, I installed a time-lapse camera to capture the stream's water level and validate the sound recordings.

The structure of the work begins with the construction and development of the audio sensor. The focus is on selecting and explaining the chosen hardware and demonstrating the software's functionality. Further, we focus on the field test. Besides the site, the manner of installation of the sensor plays an important role. Subsequently, the data evaluation section explains the methods for data processing of the audio and image files. The result and the discussion follow after the method chapter. Summing up the work, the conclusion serves as a guide to the most important findings. Ultimately, I highlight limitations and opportunities by using sound to determine water level and suggest priorities for future research.

2 Methods

In this chapter, I will describe the methods through 3 sections: *data acquisition*, *field test*, and *data evaluation*, and thus show the successive steps of the method. Essentially, the method combines the two collected data types, images, and audio files, to determine the water level in an ephemeral stream. An important step was developing the audio sensor to record.

However, the data was only obtainable after developing the audio sensor that records the sounds of IRES. I describe in detail the original work I did to build, program, test, and use this self-made audio recording device. Comparatively, the section on the image sensor is kept short, since the camera does not have to be developed and is already a ready-to-go device specifically to monitor an area. I carried out the data evaluation of the audio and image files with Matlab (2022b). After processing the audio and image files with its method, I correlated the two obtained data series. Using the exponential regression function to calculate the relationship, we can calculate the water level only from sounds.

2.1 Data acquisition

2.1.1 Audio sensor

The core of the datalogger is the Teensy 3.2 microcontroller. Together with the audio shield and the power supply unit, it forms the autonomous datalogger to record sounds. In general, the sensor is divided into three different components, where each fulfills specific tasks:

1. Power supply, with voltage converter, solar panel, and lithium-polymer(LiPo) battery
2. Microcontroller with real-time clock (RTC) to keep time stamp
3. Audio shield with the connected microphone

In addition to the three components, two light-emitting diodes (LED) indicate with the green LED or the red LED if the sensor is behaving correctly or if an error is occurring during the initialization phase. The price of the parts of the data logger, including solar panel and solar power manager, is around 155 swiss francs (CHF) (overview of costs in the appendix in table 5). In the following paragraphs, I will detail the individual components of the audio sensor and explain each of its functions.

Audio sensor performance: The goal of the sensor is to record audio with a self-defined interval. To do so, technical objectives were defined. Technical objectives the sensor must meet are crucial in developing a technical device. The following goals apply to the audio sensor; the sensor must stay in situ and perform correctly regardless of the meteorological conditions. Therefore, I defined hardware and software objectives for the sensor to prove its outdoor durability. The sensor

Figure 2: *Block schematic of audio sensor*

Three components of the audio sensor:
Power supply, microcontroller, audio shield + microphone

must be able to work in an alpine context in the given temperature range and weather conditions for at least two months. The following list shows the required hardware components and, subsequently, software functions of the sensor to meet the defined objectives.

Mandatory hardware components

- Microcontroller, which is capable of performing audio-recording tasks
- Audio recording unit includes a microphone and the corresponding electronic parts to enable audio recording (audio control and audio buffer)
- SD-card slot to store the recorded audio files
- Real Time Clock to verify recorded audio files with a timestamp
- Sufficient power supply including solar panel, DC-DC converter (DC = direct current), and battery
- Waterproof mounting setup including a waterproof case

Optional hardware components:

- Digital signal processing (DSP) to process audio file on board

Mandatory software functions

- Supporting Arduino integrated development environment (IDE) for programming
- Uninterrupted run time from the audio sensor
- Energy conservation methods to reduce power consumption

- Data quality: Errors logging data: How many errors occurred during the data sampling (Goal: valid audio files >95%)

This list of components and software functions defined the target that was the starting point for the development of the sensor. Further in the thesis, we will evaluate whether the predefined goals were met and whether the set target was appropriate for the sensor’s development.

Teensy 3.2:

Considering all the available microcontrollers to meet the set goals for the audio sensor, I selected the Teensy 3.2. The decisive reason for the choice of the Teensy 3.2 was the possibility of expanding with the available audio shield from the same supplier. The Teensy 3.2 is produced by the company of Paul J Stoffregen and Robin C Coon (PJRC) (PJCR, 2022a). It runs on an ARM Cortex-M4 processor at 72 MHz and provides the board with 256 kilobytes of flash, 64 kilobytes of RAM, and 2 kilobytes of EEPROM. The device supports all conventional interfaces such as Serial, I2C, SPI, Analog, I2S, and CAN. In total, the Teensy has 34 digital in/ output pins. A PC or a USB hub with 5 V powers the Teensy 3.2 with a USB cable. During the field test, the Teensy was powered by a Lithium-Polymer battery (LiPo) of 3.7 V, which was boosted to 5 V by a DC-DC converter. A USB cable was used to connect the power unit and the microcontroller. In normal mode, the Teensy draws about 56 mA (self-measured with a multimeter while running on the available test code on the Teensy website (https://www.pjrc.com/teensy/low_power.html)).

Figure 3: *Teensy 3.2* (PJCR, 2022b)

A 32.768 kilohertz (kHz) crystal, soldered on the backside of the Teensy, recorded the time. The selected crystal has a drift of ± 20 particles per million [ppm] at 32.786 kHz, whereas better crystals have a lower drift down to ± 5 ppm at 32.786 kHz. The drift of an RTC is displayed with the unit ppm. The lower the ppm, the lower the frequency drift, which is responsible for keeping the exact time. Due to delivery problems, I could not get a better crystal in time and had to work with the ± 20 ppm drift. The daily drift from an RTC with 20 ppm drift is 1,728 seconds. In 60 days, the drift from the actual time is 1 minute and 43 seconds. A 3.3 V coin cell powers the crystal to keep time even when the controller is set to sleeping mode, and several essential parts of the microcontroller, like keeping time, are turned off to reduce power.

Figure 4: *Audio Shield from Teensy (PJRC, 2022)*
Microphone is missing on image

Audio shield and microphone: PJRC produces an audio shield for the Teensy (PJRC, 2022b,a). Besides the recording unit, with a microphone and memory chip for buffering audio, the shield is equipped with an SD-card slot and thus includes two essential sensor components for the audio sensor on the audio shield. Additionally, the audio board is well documented, and a graphical software audio design tool exists. This tool allows the user to design software code for recording quickly.

The recording unit of the audio shield is the corresponding microphone (AOM-6738P-R). Power consumption was a deciding factor for the selected microphone. Since the selected microcontroller only powers external added devices with maximal 5 V. The selected microphone needs 1.5 V, which the microcontroller can feed. The frequency range of the microphone is in the audible range of humans, which is of 20 Hz to 20 kHz. All the sound recordings were stored as RAW files. The RAW audio format is uncompressed audio data without headers to store information such as sampling rate or resolution (Blake, 2010). The method of recording RAW files is Pulse-Code-Modulation (PCM). With PCM first, the sound of IRES converts into an analog signal. Since the sound recording was made at 16-bit, the analog signal is represented in 65.536 digital steps (16^2). Second, the curve of the analog signal is sampled regularly at uniform intervals. Since the sampling is in uniform intervals, a continuous signal can not be described; instead, the sample is discrete in time. Therefore the represented value at a sampling step approximates the analog signal. The sample rate is 44'100. Hence, the approximation is made 44'100 times within a second.

The microphone's sensitivity is -38 decibels (dB), and the signal-to-noise (dBA) is 60. Signal-to-noise is a unit of how much the signal stands out from the background noise to extract information from the audio signal reliably. The sensitivity is a unit of the amount of output the microphone gives at a particular input. These specifications determine the range of sound and the conversion into audio data. The sensitivity is relevant to calculate the sound pressure level (SPL). And

signal-to-noise is negligible because the same type of microphone recorded the relevant audio files; therefore, the recording specifications are the same over the entire recording period.

The Teensy 3.2 also meets the optional hardware component with digital sound processing (DSP) on board. With the processing tool, recorded audio files can be evaluated directly. As a result, the microcontroller can do a spectrum analysis with a fast fourier transformation (FFT). Consequently, the sensor processes the collected data, and the researcher spends less time post-processing the data. The audio file processing in detail will be explained in chapter 2.3.1. Unfortunately, processing on board was not included in the current software but remains a valuable feature for future software and sensor improvements. Instead, I processed the audio file on a computer with Matlab (R2002b).

Figure 5: *Signal over time and frequency (NTI Audio, 2022)*

FFT is a more efficient way to do the discrete fourier transform (DFT). The DFT decomposes the periodic signal (audio signal over time; see figure 5 red graph) into individual time discrete spectral components by superimposing many sine and cosine functions (figure 5 purple waves). The sine and cosine functions, each with their frequencies and amplitudes, form the frequency range of the continuous audio signal. As a result, the DFT converts a continuous signal into a time-discrete signal. For sound, this is the continuous audio signal converting into time discrete decibels per hertz (figure 5 blue area plot). The audio shield supports a 16-bit, 44.1 kHz (CD quality) sample rate. It is specially designed for the Teensy 3.0-3.6 and the newer Teensy 4.0 and 4.1. A pin socket and header allow the shield to mount directly on the Teensy. Once mounted on the Teensy, it accesses the required pins for audio data, audio control, volume potentiometer, SD-card, and memory chip. The audio shield is designed to record and play audio files. Therefore, many in-

and output lines for audio complement the shield. To record sound, only SD-card, audio control, and memory chip are necessary. The sound is converted from the microphone into an electrical signal, which is buffered by the audio control in the memory chip. When the buffered block of data reaches the size of 512 bytes, it is stored on the SD-card. It is impossible to store the data constantly on the SD-card; it must first be buffered in the memory chip. Buffering first is the most efficient way for the SD-library to save data on the SD-card. The audio files are saved on a 32 gigabyte SD-card of SanDisk Ultra A1, which is recommended by the inventor of the audio shield (PJCR, 2022b).

In the field, the sensor recorded 10 seconds every two two hours. During the 2-hour interval, the power consumption of the sensor is reduced. Since I did not know how long the power supply would last before I entered the field, the interval was rather high. A ten-second recording uses about 882 kilobyte of memory. Therefore, for a recording interval of 10 seconds every two hours, the SD-card has storage space for approximately 3020 days (8.2 years) or around 36240 recordings if the recording time of 10 seconds remains.

Integrated development environment Arduino: Currently, the best-documented programming language for microcontrollers is Arduino. Arduino is based on the programming language C++ and is designed to program microcontrollers. With its large community that uses and develops Arduino, Arduino provides much support in forums or with videos on the internet. The open-source software allows users to develop and share libraries and example codes easily. The Teensy I use is compatible with Arduino, and example codes for the audio shield exist that have been written in the Arduino-specific programming language. To program a Teensy, a software extension for the Arduino IDE called Teensyduino is installed on the computer. A USB cable is used to connect the computer and the microcontroller. The software code is transmitted via this connection, and information is received regarding ongoing processes on the microcontroller in real-time.

Program code: In the following part, I will explain the code of the recording unit and how the code is structured. The program code is structured into three parts. The first part is the configuration area where the used libraries are included, the register for restart is defined, the audio and sleep mode configuration are made, all the used pins are assigned, the global variables are defined, and the buffer size is set. In the configuration area, the user can change values for the recording time or interval period between a recording. The second part is the setup part, where the RTC, memory chip of the audio shield, LED for indication of the initialization, interval timer, sleep mode, and SD-Card are initialized. In the third part, the microcontroller executes the code repeatedly in a loop.

Four libraries with code examples were used to develop the essential software functions. The used

libraries are listed below.

- SD-Card read and write
www.github.com/arduino-libraries/SD/tree/master/examples/ReadWrite
- Audio record and play
www.github.com/PaulStoffregen/Audio/tree/master/examples/Recorder
- DeepSleep
www.github.com/duff2013/Snooze/tree/master/examples/deepsleep
- RTC for Teensy
www.github.com/PaulStoffregen/Time/tree/master/examples/TimeTeensy3

The software approach in the loop used different modes for separate code functions. Each mode calls different functions and changes to the next mode after it is finished or an interval expires. Therefore, the loop section of the code constantly checks which mode is active and executes the active mode. The following part will explain the function according to its mode.

Figure 6: Flowchart of program code from the audio sensor

Mode 0 Initialization: The datalogger indicates, with the green LED, that everything is working by turning on the green led. But if some error occurs, the datalogger flashes the red LED: After mode 0, the controller changes to mode 1.

Mode 1 Logfile: After every start or restart, the controller creates a log file. The log file contains essential information about the current time and date, duration of recording, and sleep interval. The user understands through the log file what the settings of the software code were and when the data logger was started. At the end of Mode 0, the controller changes to mode 2.

Mode 2 DeepSleep: In the *DeepSleep* mode, the controller turns off several power-consuming parts, and the power consumption drops to around 10 mA. The length of the *DeepSleep* is defined by the interval period between the recordings. When this period elapses, the controller exits *DeepSleep*, and the function to start recording is called. This start recording function creates the audio

file and folder, where the folder's name is the current day's date, and the file's name is the current time. If the folder of the current day already exists, the controller will skip creating the folder. Besides creating the directory, the controller starts the interval for the recording. The set interval for recording is ten seconds. After starting the recording and its interval, the audio sensor changes to mode 3.

Mode 3 Record: The microcontroller keeps recording and stores the audio until 2 blocks of bytes are complete on the memory chip of the audio shield. Afterward, it saves the byte blocks in the corresponding audio file on the SD-card. The mode continues recording until the interval for the recording is exceeded and calls up the stop-recording function. The stop-recording function stops and saves the remaining bytes of the memory chip on the SD-card. Before changing the mode, the controller checks the recently recorded audio file size. Some recordings failed, and this malfunction kept causing problems in the code. Therefore, I introduced a software restart when the file size equals 0 bytes. A software restart prevents the data logger from keeping creating invalid audio files. To restart the audio sensor, the software calls the register for a software reboot. After a software reboot, the mode is 1. Otherwise, if the recording is successful, the sensor mode is changed to two, where the datalogger goes into *DeepSleep*.

Power supply and energy conservation: During the field test, a battery powers the Teensy. The 3.7 V 2000 milliampere hours (mAh) battery is connected to the solar power management module. In addition, the solar panel is also connected to the solar power module, which charges the 3.7 V battery when there is enough sunlight. Further, the module powers the Teensy with 5 V via a USB port. Therefore, the module is a DC-DC converter to change voltages. The solar panel reaches a voltage up to 19 V, converted to 3.7 V for the battery or 5 V for the Teensy by the module. The connection between the battery and the solar power management module is bidirectional to charge on the one hand and to power the controller on the other. The charge capacity is limited to 2000 mAh for the LiPo. A fully charged battery powers the Teensy for about 5 days. To align the solar panel, two aluminum plates were bent and fastened with screws on a wooden board (see Figure 11).

Table 1: *Current consumption in the different software modes. (Measurement with multimeter)*

Mode	Duration of mode	Current consumption [ma]
Logging Mode	00h 01min 00s	$\sim 59mA (\pm 1.0)$
DeepSleep Mode	01h 59min 46s	$\sim 10mA (\pm 0.5)$
Record Mode	00h 00min 14s	$\sim 66mA (\pm 2.0)$

Three modes are active in the code loop, resulting in different current draw consumption. The *DeepSleep* mode consumes the lowest amount of power. During this mode, the power consumption

decreases by around 85% (see Table 11) compared to the record mode. In recording mode, the sensor consumes about 75 mA; in Logfile mode, the sensor consumes around 59 mA. Since the audio recording only takes 14 seconds (10 seconds recording and 4 seconds saving the recorded data), the initialization phase runs only once when starting the Teensy. The audio sensor spends most of its time in *DeepSleep* mode consuming about 10 mA.

Figure 7: *Open audio sensor case*

Left-edge: 3.7V LiPo battery
Left: Solar power management module
Right-bottom: Teensy with audio shield
Right-top: Coin cell battery for RTC

Case waterproofing: Keeping electronics dry was essential. Humidity or even water inside the box could cause damage to the electronics. The housing complies with the IP67 standard. IP67 standard means dust and waterproof out for a certain, short period. However, the case needed two accessible ports from outside. The drilled ports were the power connection between the solar panel and the solar power management module and, second, the microphone, positioned outside the box to make unhindered recordings. Both the cable to the solar panel and the microphone were attached to the case using a cable gland to prevent water from entering the case. In addition, the microphone had a windscreen, which, when wet, quickly absorbs moisture. A water protection shield from a plastic ring made from a used multi-purpose cup protects the audio sensor and microphone from water intrusion. In addition, the microphone output was attached to the bottom of the housing to obtain direct sound waves from the stream and protect the microphone from raindrops.

2.1.2 Image sensor

Next to the audio sensor is a time-lapse camera installed. The TLC 200 is a time-lapse camera with a movable lens to select the desired recording area. The device offers a resolution of 1280x720 points and weighs only 120 grams (Brinno, 2022). Moreover, the movable arm extends the shooting range noticeably to capture any desired area (See figure 11). In addition, Brinno offers waterproof housing, which makes the camera very useful for outdoor shooting. With a set interval of 30 minutes, the camera can record for 78 days. The data is stored on an SD-card as a movie file (.avi). Four AA batteries powered the TLC 200.

2.2 Field test

After the development phase of the sensor, the sensor was installed in the field in the summer of 2022, from July 27th until the end of September. This chapter focuses on the selected study site and, afterward, on how the sensor was set up in the field to record the best possible data.

Figure 8: Valley of Nant

Retrieved at <https://s.geo.admin.ch/9b883b2fb3> (Date: 2022-11-09).

2.2.1 Field site

Valle de Nant (*translated to english Valley of Nant*) is in the western Swiss Alps and has a catchment area of 13.4 km². It is located in the catchment area of the Röhne (Michelon et al., 2021). Furthermore, it has been a protected area since 1969 and is of national importance for Switzerland in terms of biodiversity (Université de Lausanne, 2022). At least it has been protected and is suitable for research on less-impacted landscapes. The streams in the Valley of Nant are strongly influenced by snow. About 60 % of groundwater and stream flow is caused by snow melt (Beria

et al., 2017). The Valley of Nant corresponds to the needed condition to test the audio sensor since the area is equipped with meteorological stations to get a complete data set with relevant data for the stream and the Valley of Nant has several ephemeral streams (Mächler et al., 2021). The meteorological stations in the area should provide information about the origin of a stream flow. Unfortunately, the meteorological stations in Valley of Nant had a technical issue during the testing period of the audio sensor and stored no data. Therefore, other meteorological stations near the valley were chosen. More about the choice of the meteorological stations can be found in chapter 2.3.4.

Figure 9: *Potential ephemeral streams: southeast in the valley*
 Retrieved at <https://s.geo.admin.ch/9b6daa530a>(Date:2022-11-04).

The overview map from Valley of Nant in figure 9 shows that several side streams feed the main river *L’Avançon de Nant*, which flows north through the valley. Hence, many of the side streams represented potential measurement opportunities. Streams with significant variability in the flow regime were selected to test the sensor. Side streams only contain water when snow or a glacier is melting or during and after rainfall events. Besides the variability of the water amount in the stream, a site with no disturbance sounds by the main river was crucial. On the first day in Valley of Nant in May 2022, the goal was to identify suitable sites. Trees and roots are good places to mount the sensor and often provide a good visual overview of the stream. In addition, the sensor on a tree is also well-protected from wildlife. In addition, the trees and roots had to be close to

the potential stream course but still protected from interfering noises from the main river. Observing as many changes as possible in the flow regime during the testing period was essential. Mächler et al. (2021) investigated the river system in the Valley of Nant and declared IRES in the Valley of Nant. Therefore, I installed the sensor at the northernmost of the three river courses. During the first visit to the Valley of Nant in May 2022, I observed water flow in this stream *La Tsabou*. But on the installation Day (2022-07-27), I observed no water flow at the site of the sensor installed in the stream at 14:00. However, about 100 meters upstream, water seeped into the riverbed. I expected to record water flow by the sensor when the snowpacks melt at a higher rate. Therefore, I expected to register, besides precipitation also, snow melt events as a flow event at the sensor site.

Figure 10: *Location of Sensor and Catchment Area of La Tsabou (0.60 km²)*
Retrieved at <https://s.geo.admin.ch/9b6d8ef3e5> (Date: 2022-11-04).

La Tsabou has a catchment area of around 0.61 km², and the highest point of the catchment area is 2811 meters above sea level. The peak *Petit Muveran* is the highest place in the catchment area. The coordinates of the sensor site are 46° 13' 49" N and 7° 06' 12" E. The geological map of the catchment area reveals a karst area in the heights from about 2450 meters up to 2600 meters above sea level (Rion, 2016). In conclusion, not the entire amount of a rainfall event ends up in La Tsabou. Instead, some water will flow underground through karst passages directly into the valley.

2.2.2 Mounting setup of sensor

The sensor and the solar panel were mounted on a wooden board (figure 11). Then I attached the board to a tree with two tension belts. I wanted to avoid damaging the tree by mounting and letting the wooden board directly on the tree for more than two months. Therefore, I protected the tree with a military sheet from possible injuries. Improper installation on the tree for several months could lead to lasting damage to the tree.

Since I was unsure where exactly the water would run off in the stream bed, I was looking for a position close to different possible stream courses. Also, the sensor I wanted to mount the sensor relatively close to the tree to avoid sound disturbance by the main stream. If the sensor is next to the tree, the tree functions as a sound shield from the main stream. In my case, I mounted the sensor on a tree. The tree is between possible stream courses, and the distance to the stream was about 2-3 meters away.

Figure 11: *Sensor board mounted at the tree in the field site*

2.3 Data evaluation

After the sensor is used in the field, it must be tested for reliability. Therefore deals this chapter with the sensor performance. The audio sensor performance is evaluated against the targets set at the beginning of the development (chapter 2.1.1). Furthermore, all data collected in the field test were evaluated collectively using sound and image processing, which also will be explained in more detail in this chapter.

2.3.1 Sound processing

In order to process the audio data for scientific research from the sensor directly, pre-processing steps had to be performed. All recordings were in a RAW audio format. First, the uncompressed

audio format was converted into waveform audio file format (WAV) to process the audio files with the code of Osborne et al. (2021) code. Sound eXchange (SoX) is an app to convert different audio formats with the command line (Sourceforge, 2022). I coded a batch to convert all the audio files to WAV by SoX. After converting, the data were ready to process. In the following section, I will explain the process of the Matlab code in more detail. To use the audio files scientifically, I need to know the hertz of each frequency. The dB at one hertz (Hz) gives an understanding of the sound. To do so, first, I performed the FFT to get the dB at each Hz. The calculated dB value varies enormously from Hz to Hz. Therefore, I summarized the Hz in classes with a range of 1000 Hz. The median is a better indicator in this case than the average, where high and low peaks of the frequency would influence the data strongly. According to Ohki et al. (1995), it is more beneficial to calculate the median for recurring patterns. The measurement unit used for the expression at a Hz is Sound Pressure Level (SPL). Then sound pressure level is a standard indicator for sound and is measured in decibels (dB SPL). SPL correlates with human perception of loudness (Long, 2014). As decibel is a logarithmic unit of measure, an increase of 6 decibels doubles the actual audible volume. SPL takes the sensitivity of the microphone into account. The selected microphone records in the frequency range of 20 Hz to 20 kHz. The frequency bandwidths chosen for the median range from 50 Hz to 19 kHz since the frequency response has informative values only in this range (appendix figure 29). Osborne et al. (2021) added a so-called low median filter to filter out interfering noise (i.e., wind, cowbells, or birds), too. The idea behind the filter for interfering noise is that the interfering noise only affects the recording for a short sequence of some seconds but not the entire 10-second recording. That is why the code divided the 10-second audio files into a sequence of 1 second. After splitting the 10-second audio file, the FFT is performed for each of the ten sequences and calculates the median. Then the code checks which of the 10 chunks has the lowest median in SPL dB. If noise affected a part of the recording, this chunk would have a higher median. Therefore, the code selects the lowest median, and we can be sure that no interfering noise affects the data evaluation.

2.3.2 Image processing

During the observation phase, the time-lapse camera was installed to capture a picture every 30 minutes. The images were referenced with a time stamp. To improve the image quality in darkness, the night mode was turned on, which increased the brightness of the images. Still, the image could not be processed due to the darkness at night. The daytime data were used to verify the water's presence and level. This was done by image analysis. Therefore a similar project of CrowdWater Project in Zurich served as an example (Seibert et al., 2019; Strobl et al., 2020). The researchers motivated people to gauge different stream-relevant data in the CrowdWater project. The attendants of the study estimated the stream's height and width and its velocity of the stream. Also,

they estimated the water level class by having a virtual stream level guide inserted in a picture as a reference. As a result, the estimated stream level class had fewer outliers and was close to the measured water level. In contrast to the estimated width, height, and velocity, the water level class had fewer outliers. Therefore, a reference measure was placed in the stream bed to add a scale to the images. In the subsequent image processing, I designed a virtual reference scale, which was used as a layer for the time-lapse image to determine the water level. Figure 12 shows the reference scale I placed into the stream bed. Besides this image, I set the reference scale a second time into the riverbed at a different location. The set reference scale in the stream bed (figure 12) allowed me to link the two reference scales to create the virtual scale. From the CrowdWater project, it was known that determining the water height with a virtual scale is prone to errors. Therefore the researchers of the CrowdWater project created classes of water levels to define more manageable water levels. To calculate the uncertainty of my experimental water level determination, I determined the water level a second time. However, the rerun was only limited to the images of a stream flow. With the determined level from the second run, I calculated the uncertainty with the standard deviation between the two data series.

Figure 12: Reference depth gauge

Figure 13: Virtual scale on image

Figure 14: Virtual scale
Width of stream = magenta
Flow direction = yellow

Figure 15: Virtual scale on time-lapse image

The time-lapse camera can only record videos instead of single images. I had to convert each frame of the video into a single image. Then, the code in Matlab looped through every image, and the virtual scale was added as the top layer on the image. The user of the code can determine the water

level by clicking on the scale. As figure 13 and 15 show, the width of the stream bed is defined by the magenta line. By increasing the water level, the width of the stream flow changes as well, and the magenta line helped to determine the corresponding water level. The use of the virtual scale adds a metric reference to the image. Then I wrote a code that went through each image and applied the virtual scale. By clicking on the surface, I could determine the water level. The code captures the location on the screen clicked by the mouse and obtains an X- and Y-coordinate pixel value. The X-coordinates had no meaning because they only referred to the image's width, but the Y values were converted to centimeters. Then the water level was appended to the time of the image in a table. The limitation of the images is the darkness at night. If an image was dark, I could press any letter on the keyboard and the time of the image was noted with *dark*. This made it easier to exclude the not usable images.

2.3.3 Audio and image relationship

The audio data aims to determine the water elevation in La Tsabou. For this purpose, I selected the nearest data points in time of the two data series, audio and image. Unfortunately, both have different time intervals. However, since the time-lapse images were taken every 30 minutes, the closest interval to an audio recording is a maximum of 15 minutes. Due to the different temporal resolutions, differing data values might be collected regarding the water quantity since a high water quantity variability emanates from an ephemeral stream. Interpolating the water level of the images was not an option since the water level can change quickly, and the average deviation was most often not 15 minutes and therefore gave a more meaningful value from the closest in time.

2.3.4 Supplementary data for validation

Precipitation data: Ideally, we would have precipitation data for the same period to analyze the flow events in La Tsabou. However, the meteorological station La Chaux in the Valley of Nant of SensorScope had a technical error. The data from the LUFFT WS 400 had gaps. The missing data gaps are marked as grey areas in the lowest barplot in figure 16. Therefore, I identified four different meteorological stations of MeteoSwiss, which are located close to the Valley of Nant

Table 2: *Closest precipitation meteorological stations from sensor site*

Station name	Altitude	LV95 E	LV95 N	Distance to audio sensor
Bex (BEX)	403.5 m asl.	2'565'805.470	1'121'511.260	8.51 km
Derborence (VSDER)	1368.0 m asl.	2'584'114.480	1'126'364.280	11.85 km
Evionnaz (EVI)	484.0 m asl.	2'568'196.350	1'114'693.340	7.93 km
Sorniot-Lac Inférieur (VSSOR)	1992.0 m asl.	2'573'829.410	1'112'848.350	7.06 km

The first and most crucial factor for the precipitation sensor location was the altitude above sea level (asl). The secondary was the distance, whereby all four selected sites are close enough to the audio sensor site. But in alpine regions, altitude has a more significant influence on precipitation distribution (Viviroli & Weingartner, 2004). Therefore, Sorniot-Lac Inférieur (VSSOR) was chosen as the location for the meteorological station. Since it is located at a similar altitude as the audio sensor (about 1500 meters asl). After identifying VSSOR as a suitable replacement, I kept working with its precipitation data. The precipitation data from VSSOR help understand the flow event in La Tsabou.

Figure 16: *Precipitation of the four closest meteorological stations from MeteoSwiss and SensorScope*

Eventually, the amount does not perfectly correspond to the amount in Valley of Nant. But it is likely to experience the same timing and magnitude of the precipitation events in the Valley of Nant when an event was registered in VSSOR.

Stream flow event: Stream flow events were defined as an event with surface discharge. The discharge must last longer than two hours to record with the audio sensor. Before and after the event, no surface runoff is visible or audible. I detected eight-stream flow events during the observation period.

Table 3: *Information about each stream flow event*

Nr.	Start event	End event	Duration	# Data points
1	2022-07-28 16:30:17	2022-07-29 06:30:31	14h 00min 14s	4
2	2022-07-29 10:30:35	2022-07-30 06:30:55	29h 59min 55s	7
3	2022-08-05 16:53:29	2022-08-06 15:13:51	22h 30min 22s	6
4	2022-08-17 17:58:18	2022-08-19 20:09:08	50h 10min 50s	15
5	2022-08-26 11:36:31	2022-08-27 09:36:53	22h 00min 22s	7
6	2022-09-07 18:51:27	2022-09-09 11:15:30	40h 24min 03s	10
7	2022-09-09 19:15:38	2022-09-10 13:15:56	18h 00min 18s	5
8	2022-09-15 17:28:00	2022-09-16 17:28:24	24h 00min 24s	8

3 Results

This section presents the results and findings of sensor development and field tests. We will first look at the development of the audio sensor and how its performance influenced the results. Then we focus on the audio and image sensors and their corresponding data. The structure of the chapter shows chronologically how I evolved from the development of the audio sensor to the data analysis and mirrored the structure we already used for the methods of the thesis.

3.1 Data acquisition

3.1.1 Audio sensor

During the entire field test, the audio sensor recorded audio files from 2022-07-28 to 2022-09-25. In this period, the device recorded 630 audio files. 21 out of the 630 audio files were invalid due to software issues. After the sensor made an invalid audio recording, this error remained for the subsequent recordings. The subsequent recordings were also all invalids. Only a software restart solved the reoccurring error. Therefore, I have implemented a restart function into the code. Therefore at the end of the loop, the sensor checks if the recorded file is empty (see chapter 2.1.1 figure 6). If the file is empty, the sensor restarts the software code and creates a new logfile. In general, the performance of the recording is satisfactory. At the beginning of the development, a reliability value of the recording of plus 95% was set as a target. The achieved value of 96.67% meets the predefined goal. The sensor turned off from 2022-08-20 at 00:00 to 2022-08-21 at 19:00 due to an unidentified error. Two days after the incident, I restarted the sensor, after which everything worked perfectly again. In the entire summer operation, the sensor switched off a total of 3 times without understandable reasons. The sensor issued an error message generally appearing when the SD-card is missing once during restart. However, in this case, the SD-card was inserted correctly.

Another finding during the deployment was the functionality of the RTC. After the first unplanned shutdown of the sensor, the RTC no longer worked properly. Then the time had to be adjusted manually. This time-consuming step was done on the computer and not in the field.

Table 4: *Table of error events*

Date error event	Duration off-time	# Lost data
2022-08-19 22:09:10	45h 05min 31s	22
2022-09-16 21:28:28	113h 07min 52s	56
2022-09-25 22:46:20	121h 13min 40s	60

3.1.2 Image sensor

The time-lapse camera did not cause any problems during the entire field test. As expected, photos were taken in 30 minutes intervals and saved in a movie file. In addition, the battery charge was enough for the whole summer. However, I replaced the battery during a maintenance visit for prevention. The change in the battery did not influence the camera's functioning or the recordings.

3.2 Field test

3.2.1 Field site

I expected stream flow events to occur regularly from the first location selected. I assumed that the snow packs above the stream melt during the summer and a daily runoff would appear in the stream like Mächler et al. (2021) observed. Unfortunately, this was not the case and, as mentioned, I was only able to register a total of eight stream flow events (See table 3 in chapter 2.3.4).

3.2.2 Mounting setup

During the entire deployment, I had no problems with on-site installation. No animal and no storm damaged the station. Protecting the tree with a canopy proved to be of limited use because, under the blanket, waterlogging occurred, which softened the tree's bark and provided a location for spider nests. By the end of the monitoring period, I removed the blanket and the spider nests. The installation took about 5-10 minutes and required only basic tools (screwdriver and strap). Since one can mount most of the equipment onto the board from home, the only work remaining in the field is to protect the tree with a military blanket and fasten the straps around the tree. Throughout the summer, I tested the battery's voltage from the audio sensor at each maintenance visit. The voltage was always around 4.12V, corresponding to about 100% charge of the battery.

3.3 Data evaluation

3.3.1 Sound processing

The first plot shows a stream flow event during a day at the 19 different frequency bands. The visualization of figure 17 gives us an understanding of the different SPL at different frequency bands. However, the visualization can also be deceptive, considering decibel is a logarithmic measure. If the perceived loudness is doubled, this increases by 6 dB. So, the difference between 40 dB to 50 dB and 20 dB to 40 dB is greater in absolute volume.

(a) 2022/07/29 SPL of entire frequency range

(b) 10:23:52 no stream flow

(c) 16:23:52 stream flow

Figure 17: All 12 sound files of 2022-07-29 with every frequency bandwidth

Every line on the XY-diagram represents one audio recording of 2022-07-29. We experienced a stream flow event on this day and no water flow. Thus, each line on the diagram has a similar shape but differs from the height on the Y-axis. The images on the right side show the stream bed at a similar time. The upper-right image is captured at 10:23:52, 7 minutes earlier than the audio sensor recorded at 10:30:35. As we can see, no water is flowing, and in the XY-diagram, the line of 10:30:35 is one of the lowest. In comparison, at 16:23:52, the image sensor captured a picture with water flow. The water level at that time was 9.4 centimeters, according to the calculation with the virtual scale. Also, about 7 minutes later, the audio sensor and the recording corresponding to line 16:30:41 are marked with magenta. The turquoise line above represents discharge in the stream. Considering all the recordings, we observe higher SPL dB in the frequency range from 0.05 kHz to 3 kHz. After that, between 3 to 7 kHz, certain SPL levels stagnate between 37 to 42 SPL dB. From the higher SPL values, we derive the stream flow events. Those which do not show any stream flow event decrease over the frequency range of 3-17 kHz from approximately 20 SPL dB, and increase up to 27 SPL dB. Regardless of whether stream flow could be observed on the images, all curves decrease after 17 kHz. That means we observe a decrease of SPL by 4-7 dB. Whereby those with stream flow events show a stronger decrease than those without.

From figure 17, we can see the change in stream flow on that day with the use of sound. The stream flow decreased continuously during the night, and at 04:30, the stream flow stopped. After that, we did not observe any stream flow until 12:30. At 12:30, there was a strong increase, which remained constant for four hours, and then the stream flow decreased slightly and remained continuously

high until the end of the day.

Besides stream flow, other noises can cause the SPL to rise above its normal value. The low median filter filters many of the interfering noises. Still unclear is the influence of rain on SPL. On September 10th, 2022, we found the three sound states at intervals of two hours each. I observed that the SPL in dB at 0.05-1 kHz is 38.77 dB with no rain and no stream flow, and with rain, it increases by only 0.06 dB to 38.83 dB (figure 18).

Figure 18: Rain in comparison to no stream flow and stream flow in [SPL db]

3.3.2 Audio and image relationship

Unfortunately, not all data were valid to evaluate. Two outliers have been identified in the data evaluation process. First, I will explain why these two data points were declared as an outlier. Second, we look at the relationship between the water level from the images and the SPL values from the audio files.

Outliers: The image sensor could almost verify all audio files by the presence or absence of stream flow. A verified value is when the visible and acoustic data points either show stream flow or no stream flow. The two outliers are shown in figure 19 (a) and figure 19 (b). At the first

(a) *Time audio recording: 19:58:20*
SPL at 0.05-1 kHz: 52.71 dB

(b) *Time audio recording: 13:36:33*
SPL at 0.05-1 kHz: 41.39 dB

Figure 19: 2 *Outliers*

event, water is audible, and no water appears on the image, while at the second event, no water is audible, even though the images show a stream flow event. I verified the audio files by manually listening to the audio files. The time difference in the first example is 4:24 minutes and in the second example 7:21 minutes. We will discuss potential explanations in chapter 4 of the thesis. The outliers were excluded from calculating the function for the relationship between audio and image data points.

Relationship of water level and SPL: To get a better understanding of the relationship between water height and sound pressure level, we must examine the frequency ranges and the difference SPL between each recording. Therefore, I have compared the determined water level with the help of the virtual scale and the frequency range. Important for further analysis is to find out which frequency range is best suited for further analysis. Figure 20 shows the relationship between the SPL of each Hz range and the water level based on the images. The list with all values for each frequency range for the exponential function is in the appendix in the table 6.

Figure 20: Every frequency bandwidth and its R^2

To calculate the relationship between the two variables, I selected the closest corresponding audio file based on the recording times of the images. As already mentioned in chapter 2.3.3, the difference in time is a maximum of 15 minutes. All night recordings due to the darkness were not included in the calculation for the images. After these conditions, I had 336 data points showing the correlation. Most of the data points are at 0 centimeter water level. There is a total of 289 values with 0 centimeter water level. The remaining 47 values influence the regression curve in height. In all 19 plots, I left out the outliers. Those are not in the plot.

Figure 21: R^2 of all 19 frequency bandwidths

The R^2 value differs from 0.95 to 0.85. The coefficient of determination, also called R^2 , is the dispersion of one value from the regression respectively relationship between the audio and image data. In Figure 21, the frequency range of 0.05-1kHz has the highest R^2 (marked with the red dot in figure 21). The frequency range with the highest R^2 will be used to calculate the water level. It is evident that, between 0.05-3 kHz, a similar R^2 is achieved. The R^2 is around 0.94-0.95. After that, we observe a steady R^2 value in the frequency ranges of 3-11 kHz about 0.9, while after that, the R^2 value fluctuates between 0.9 and 0.85 at 19 kHz it decreased to approximately 0.85.

Figure 22: Audio files are included in the correlation function of water level and sound

The strongest relationship between the water level from the images with a virtual scale and the SPL in dB is R^2 0.95. The rise of the water level is exponential in comparison to the SPL. In the discussion, we will examine why the regression curve is exponential. The regression curve stops at 29.7 centimeters water level and 55.9 SPL dB because the SPL dB is the highest and therefore determines the last calculated value on the regression curve. The two outliers significantly impact the R^2 . Including the two outliers, the R^2 decreases to 0.82. Based on the regression curve, I calculated the water level with the SPL of the audio files. The blue curve in Figure 22 shows the interpolated water level based on the audio file from the SPL of the frequency range 0.05–1 kHz with the exponential relationship function. The red crosses show in figure 22 the water level based on the images. The crosses are not continuous, and in some stream flow events, especially at the beginning of September, no red crosses are visible. This was during the night, and no water level could be determined based on the dark images. As defined in chapter 2.3.4 a stream flow event is

recorded only when valid audio and images are available simultaneously. It is important to know that the audio and image files are in a two-hour interval.

Figure 23: 2 Diagrams of correlation of water level and SPL and the calculated water level with precipitation

Left diagram: SPL in dB of 0.05-1kHz vs. water level of image

Right diagram on right Y-axis: Precipitation data (VSSOR) in orange to explain stream flow events

The added precipitation data explain the stream flow events visible in figure 23. On the right y-axis of the right diagram is the inverse precipitation scale, whereas, on the left y-axis is the water level in centimeters. Regarding precipitation, the stream flow events are reasonable and caused by rain.

Calibration: The audio sensor and the water height determination method have to be useful for future users. However, to calculate the water level only based on sound, the image needs to calculate the relationship with audio. The calibration time shows how long the processes take until reasonable data can be produced based on audio. The calculation tells us how many stream flow events are needed to accurately predict future stream flow events. Based on the stream flow events of table 3 all possible combinations of events were calculated. From the combinations, the relationship in R^2 of the data points of the used stream flow events was calculated. On the X-axis, you can see the number of stream flows, and on Y-axis, how strong the R^2 relationship to the total amount of samples is (Figure 24). If you have three events, the R^2 reaches a sufficiently high value to predict the water level. The outlier of the box plot is marked with a red cross, whereas the

median is marked with a red line.

Figure 24: Number of stream flow events for accurate prediction of water level with audio

4 Discussion

In this chapter, we revisit the results, explain specific patterns found in the results, and provide information and evidence to explain the results we got. Also, we compare with the literature and return to the context of the problem. As in the previous chapters, we keep the structure of the subchapters in the same order as in the chapter method and chapter results.

4.1 Data acquisition

4.1.1 Audio sensor

One of the thesis goals was to develop an audio sensor to record audio files autonomously for two months. To achieve the goal, hardware and software goals were defined in chapter 2.1.1. The hardware goals served to select the proper hardware, while the software goal set the performance goals for the audio sensor. During the field test of the sensor in the Valley de Nant, several advantages and challenges to the measurement setup became apparent. This section will review the pros and cons and possible solutions to the challenges. My results show that the microphone and the audio shield performed well overall. Over 95% of the possible recordings were valid. The introduced restart after the file check improved the data's validity and sensor performance. The recorded audio data met the requirements for the FFT and showed a high correlation with the water level of the images. Osborne et al. (2021) previously demonstrated that low-cost microphones are suitable for water level determination. However, despite these measures, I registered three unidentified shutdowns during the deployment from June 28, 2022, onwards. The logfiles did not provide sufficient information about the malfunction. To identify the malfunction, I recommend extending the logfile with information about the size of buffered data on the different buffers and the time certain software functions take. Introducing a more detailed logfile would help to detect a malfunction. Another observation is the possible presence of moisture inside the sensor case. I noticed that after an incident, the sensor switched off during heavy rainfall. After analyzing the recorded images and audio recording, I found that, at that moment, there was extreme precipitation. Unfortunately, I could not identify the reason for the shutdown. However, I have two hypotheses for the problem. The two hypotheses are:

1. The rainfall may have caused moisture to enter the case and caused a short circuit.
2. The heavy precipitation and the resulting vibrations inside the housing may have disconnected or misdirected a connection, caused a short circuit or interrupted the power supply.

To avoid moisture inside the case, a desiccant bag is recommended. After the heavy rainfall and the shutdown, I registered an additional malfunction with the RTC. The RTC lost the saved time loading a new software code on the Teensy. It was no longer possible to store the current time, but

the sensor started the clock with the alternative timestamp (1900-01-01 00:00:00). The RTC kept working with the alternative timestamp. All the recorded files with the wrong timestamp had to be edited manually to change it to the actual time. After the field test, I resoldered the RTC and it worked flawlessly. Besides the bad connection, another issue concerning the RTC could occur during an extended testing period. A drift of the RTC is possible over long terms (Assendelft & Ilja van Meerveld, 2019). Unfortunately, an RTC with a lower time drift for the audio sensor was not available due to delivery problems. Therefore a crystal with a frequency drift of ± 20 ppm was used, whereas better crystals have a lower drift down to ± 5 ppm at 32.786 kHz (more information about the drift in chapter 3.1.1 in paragraph *Teensy 3.2*). In contrast, the power supply did not cause problems during the field test. A possible future adjustment in the power supply is using screw locks to connect the power cable at the Teensy and the solar power module. Screw locks avoid potential problems from cables disconnecting unintentionally by closing the case. In conclusion, the audio sensor is ready for use, with some caveats.

4.2 Field test

4.2.1 Field site

During the sensor development, I learned that it is helpful to get quickly to the sensor site. Unfortunately, the Valley of Nant is far from the university of Bern. By car, it takes about 1.26 hours, and by train much longer, 3.05 hours. For future testing and validation of own developed sensors, a location closer to the university make maintenance visit easier and allows for development constantly.

My results show, that the site for the sensor was still a good choice. For example, the scientific work of Mächler et al. (2021) and Foehn et al. (2018) contributed to understanding meteorological and hydrological processes in the Valley of Nant and helped to discuss the results. Often stream flow events happen when snowpacks start to melt during the day. Hence, the decisive factor was the presence of snow areas above the stream. Picture 25 shows snowpacks above the southernmost stream. In the study of Mächler et al. (2021), the researcher observed partial stream flow of the melting snow packs. Hence, from July to September 2022 stream flows because of melting snow did not occur.

Figure 25: *Snow packs above potential IRES in Valley of Nant*
Location of image: Valley Of Nant, Date of record: 2022-08-07
For a better visibility, the snow packs are colored light yellow

4.2.2 Mounting setup

The distance between the audio sensor and the stream was about 2 to 3 meters. However, the sound quality will depend on the distance to the potential stream. For comparison, Osborne et al. (2021) observed a change in the sound pressure level from 66 dB SPL to 61 dB SPL when the distance was increased by 10 meters. However, these findings are negligible for our case because I analyzed the data only from one sensor. The difference in dB gets interesting when several sensors are compared. In my case, I made no comparison with different sensor sites and preconditions. Power was never an issue for the audio sensor. Over the entire test period, the battery never got low. The solar panel was big enough and appropriately aligned to charge the battery daily.

4.3 Data evaluation

4.3.1 Sound processing

Overall, it is possible to derive the presence of water in an IRES by analyzing audio files with an FFT. As we can see in chapter 3.3.1 figure 17, the threshold for the presence of water is around 40 SPL dB at the frequency range of 0.05-1 kHz. If the SPL dB rises above 40 SPL dB in the frequency range of 0.05-1 kHz the SPL value indicates the presence of water. From the result, I observed that the highest SPL is in the frequency range of 0.05-1 kHz and is about 56 dB. No-

tably, the SPL around the frequency level of 0.05–3 kHz is considerably higher than the rest of the frequency range when water is present. The observed difference to the rest of the frequency range is between 10 to 20 dB. To explain it, we have to consider the decibels again as a measuring unit. In the area with no water and a higher SPL (0.05-3 kHz), we observe a graphically smaller difference between stream flow and no stream flow regarding SPL. The graphical difference is more significant in frequency ranges above 3 kHz. This peculiarity is related to the measurement unit dB, which is logarithmic. An increase in perceived loudness is a smaller increase in SPL dB when the base loudness is already higher. A doubling of the perceived volume at quiet sounds, the person perceives less strongly.

4.3.2 Image processing

The CrowdWater project has introduced classes for the water level to reduce the uncertainty of the determination (Strobl et al., 2020). The uncertainty in the adapted approach to determine the water level on images is ± 1.31 centimeter (figure 26).

Figure 26: Correlation of image and sound of 0.05-1 kHz with σ of water level

From image processing, I have learned that the user who determines the water level with the virtual scale must see the image clearly and in a high resolution. If one moves one pixel on the image, the result in centimeter changes, or as long as the stream flow event takes as the clearer the water gets, it gets more challenging to determine the exact water level. Clear water makes it hard to detect the edge of the stream flow. For future improvement, a scale can be permanently installed in the stream bed, allowing for efficiently deriving the water level from the images. It is also possible to automate the process by implementing a camera with the software GaugeCam. GaugeCam automatically derives the water level. More information about the GaugeCam application is on

the web on <https://gaugecam.org>.

4.4 Audio and image relationship

4.4.1 Relationship of water level and SPL

Figure 27: *Correlation of image and sound of 0.05-1 kHz*

The overall hydrological goal was to determine the water level based on the sound. The method worked very well. In figure 27, we can observe the exponential regression curve of 0.05-1 kHz SPL in dB and the water level from images. The relationship was strong with $0.95 R^2$. The high correlation allows us to accurately deduce the water level from the audio files in La Tsabou. The correlation works on almost all SPL values. If the SPL value is above 40 dB, the determination of the water level gets accurate. Therefore, the method works when stream flow occurs.

Further, I could determine the reason for the run-off at the sensor station. The reason for runoff in IRES can be snow, rain, or spring water (Paillex et al., 2020). Snow packs like in figure ?? could have caused runoff in IRES. However, the image is from the catchment area of the neighboring river. The image gives an idea of how it could look in the catchment area. The image of the snow packs was taken before I installed the sensor in the field to monitor potential run-off reasons. But by the time the sensor was installed, these snow packs had melted too much to cause run-off at the site of the sensor. A further reason for run-off is rain. Unfortunately, the precipitation data in Valley of Nant had gaps and were, therefore, of no use for explaining the stream flow event in La Tsabou. The data from VSSOR used instead explains almost all streamflow events. Precipitation

was recorded in VSSOR at the same time stream flow events occurred (See figure 23). The amount of precipitation in mountain areas is highly spatially variable by altitude (Viviroli & Weingartner, 2004). The station at VSSOR is at a more similar altitude than the meteorological station in Bex. Another possibility to determine precipitation would be radar. But, determining precipitation with radar in the Valley of Nant is challenging. Most of the Valley of Nant is in the shadow of the Swiss weather radar network (Foehn et al., 2018). In addition, I found out that for each precipitation event of at least 5 millimeters observed in VSSOR, a stream flow event occurred in La Tsabou. Therefore, I presume that the precipitation event needed to be necessary for the stream flow event in La Tsabou. The precipitation data, combined with the data from our work, suggests that there needed to be more snow in the summer of 2022 for us to observe a stream flow event at the sensor's location from June 28, 2022. The climate bulletin for winter 2021/22 from Meteo Swiss shows a decrease in precipitation in the area of Valley of Nant. The decrease was between 90-80% of the usual average of precipitation from 1901-2020 (MeteoSchweiz, 2022).

In figure 27 the regression curve is exponential. I assume that the water level in the stream bed does not increase linearly to the discharge. Speaking of the stream bed, the IRES, with its uneven stream bed and the many boulders in the stream bed, cause no laminar flow (NC Division of Water Quality, 2005; Bathurst, 2002). Phillips et al. (2018) and Minnaert (1933) state that oscillating bubbles create sound in a liquid medium. As more discharge, the more turbulence, the more air bubble, and as louder the sound of the water is. Also, the water volume increases exponentially in contrast to the water level. When I derived the water levels in the stream, I found out the critical height was 40 centimeters. If the stream is above the critical height, the river becomes extremely wide, and new courses open up. According to this finding, the stream level cannot get higher.

4.4.2 Off points

In addition to the outliers, two other values stood out in the relationship diagram. These are marked in the orange boxes in figure 28. Box 1 shows three data points, where no stream flow is usually inferred based on the SPL value. But that is why I looked at the associated pictures again and watched the audio files. In both files, a small stream flow is visible or audible. In the audio file, a quiet ripple from the water is audible. Unfortunately, it is impossible to distinguish these values at the frequency range of 0.05-1 kHz. In orange box 2, no stream flow is visible in the pictures. However, in the audio file, a helicopter is audible over the whole 10-second recording. Since the noise affected the full 10 seconds, the low-median filter could not filter the helicopter's noise.

Figure 28: Off points are marked in the orange boxes

4.4.3 Calibration

Using the defined stream flow events from chapter 2.3.4, I combined all eight stream flow events. I calculated how many stream flow events are needed to calibrate and get a reliable R^2 value to determine the water level with sound. After three stream flow events the R^2 value is good enough for water level determination. In other words, it takes between 15-33 samples of stream flows. This is the number of samples from the combination of the stream flow events with the three highest and lowest numbers of samples. To shorten the time for calibration in the future, it is important to increase the interval time of the audio recordings and the image sensor to, for example, 10 minutes. This way, calibration can be performed more accurately. However, considering the three stream flow events with the lowest water level (stream flow events 1, 2, and 7 see in table 3) of the images. The R^2 value is 0.89 and indicates the need of stream flow events that reach a high water level to make a sufficient calibration.

4.5 Limitation

A limiting factor is the sample quantity. Little stream flow samples were recorded, including information about the water level above 0 centimeters. Out of a total of 336 samples, 47 provided information about the presence of water. Unfortunately, the scarcity of snowpacks due to the winter of 2022 and the sparse precipitation in the summer of 2022 was limiting. In addition, I experienced technical problems because the audio sensor had unexpected and unidentified shut-

downs. I recommend increasing the audio sensor's interval. In image processing, the determination was challenging and limiting due to the changing water opacity and quantity. However, considering the uncertainty of the water level determination, statements can be made about the relationship with the audio. The filter for interfering noises works very well. Only alone, the low-median filter could not filter a helicopter's sound since the noise impacted the full 10-second recording. Besides the methods, there were also limitations to the audio sensor. Drawing power in the record mode of the audio sensor is high, but the 14 seconds of high-power consumption is negligible when the sensor spends most of the time in DeepSleep power-saving mode. In addition, I did not observe any power shortages on the sensor over the entire summer. So, one can easily set a shorter interval between the recordings in the future, and as a result, more data points during stream flow events would be available. As can happen with every development of a technical device, I also experienced problems in the supply chain. The Teensy 3.2 is no longer available because the chip shortage affected the Teensy production. The delayed and limited availability is bad for future applications of the audio sensor. However, the website has promised that Teensy 3.2 may be delivered again next spring <https://www.pjrc.com/store/teensy32.html>. However, there is also an alternative for the Teensy 3.2, and the Teensy 4.1 can be combined with the audio shield. However, the power consumption of Teensy 4.0 is higher than that of 3.2, which might raise new challenges. But existing problems like unexpected shutdowns or corrupted audio files could get solved by introducing a new controller. A significant disadvantage compared to the conventional measurement methods, such as graphical water detection methods with the camera, is manual calibration. As Osborne et al. (2021) found out, the SPL varies with the distance to the water. Therefore, a separate calculation must always be made for the stream with a comparative method, such as image processing.

4.6 Outlook

Future research on the developed audio sensor in IRES must be done. Due to the low costs, an extensive network of sensors can be installed in the field and spatial data acquisition of IRES is possible. The limiting factor is the determination of the water height simultaneously. On the one hand, the existing image water level detection method can be used. On the other hand, there is also the possibility of determining the water level with the help of IR sensors. Furthermore, it would be interesting to correlate the audio files with stream discharge. Since I have learned that the exponential function is related to the dB scale and the water level, it would be interesting to see how the relationship between discharge and SPL will look. I used the exponential function to calculate the relationship between the audio and image data series. An exponential function starts at the zero point. Whereas the power function does not have to cross the zero point. I recommend trying the power function to calculate the relationship.

Identifying the reasons for the unexpected shutdowns is the first step to improving the performance

of the audio sensor. As already mentioned in the discussion in chapter 4.1.1, it would be helpful to expand saved information on the logfile to understand better the code running on the Teensy and how the different memories on the Teensy are used.

Further, the Teensy 3.2 is temporarily stopped due to chip shortage. In the upcoming spring of 2023, production will be ramped up. Therefore, a switch to Teensy 4.0 has to be taken into account. The sensor performance must be re-evaluated. It could make sense to automate audio processing by performing DSP on the Teensy to get and analyze SPL values. The advantage of DSP on board is that less calculation has to be done on a computer. With the SPL values of the frequency ranges, real-time stream flow event detection is possible. Consequently, the interval between the recordings can be adjusted to collect more data during a stream flow event. Dynamic interval optimizes the power consumption, and researchers have more data on stream flow events. Power consumption is higher during stream flow events and would save power if no stream flow events occur. If we do DPS on board, you can transmit the water level in real time via, for example, LoRa or other transmitting radio technologies. The advantage of self-developed code is that it can be expanded and adapted to the desired purpose at any time.

More acoustic data of stream flows would also go hand in hand with the current advances in audio sensors in different scientific fields. Researchers need more and more machine learning for dataset analysis. However, this requires many acoustic datasets, which currently do not exist in IRES. A machine-learning approach can replace the manual calibration of the audio sensor. For example, various works, such as the Stowell et al. (2019), determine the birds' species based on birds' chirping with machine learning. They achieved a high recognition rate, and the determination also works independently of the environment. Another advantage of machine learning is the detection of hidden signals. Hidden signals are signals with low amplitudes, which are currently needed for detecting earthquakes (Rouet-Leduc et al., 2017; Stork et al., 2020).

5 Conclusion

My thesis was successful because I developed an audio sensor that could record the sound of IRES. In total, the audio sensor recorded 630 audio files from an IRES in an alpine region. Another success was the image processing to calculate the water height with a virtual scale. In a fast way, I could process with the help of a program code through each of the pictures and determine the water level. The relationship between the water level from the images and the SPL values from the audio data is strong. The strong relationship shows that, the thesis offers the possibility of determining the water level using only the audio of IRES in mountainous areas. The whole work took more than 11 months, during which the development of the sensor took place; in the summer of 2022, the sensor was in the field for two months, and afterward, the data were evaluated and analyzed. During this time, I was able to learn three important things.

- Developing and programming the audio sensor is challenging. Technical components must be carefully selected. Writing a working software code takes time. But the internet, especially for Arduino IDE, provides information in forums.
- Sound is a data source that offers a lot of potential for hydrology, which should be considered in further research projects. For research projects requiring a high resolution in space and time, self-developed audio sensors are a considerable solution.
- More is better – Higher density of the recorded data points in time and place gives a deeper data basis. This allows scientists to make even more prescient statements. Getting to a lower data resolution is always possible when less is enough.

During the entire thesis, there have been setbacks regarding sensor development.

- A big problem was the sensor's unexpected and unidentified shutdowns. No software development could be made to solve this problem. This remains a problem and needs to be addressed in the future.
- Shortage of chips results in problems in the supply chain of Teensy. Particularly in developing and planning a new device, the goal is to prevent selected components from being temporarily unavailable or out of stock. In the case of the Teensy 3.2 shortage, I recommend testing the new Teensy 4.0 with the corresponding audio shield.

Nevertheless, the thesis was successful, and the next steps for sound, IRES, and autonomous audio sensors can be addressed. I would be pleased if a person would resume the research with the audio sensor.

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6 Appendix

Table 5: *Cost of each audio sensor part*

Parts List		
Part Name	Web-Link	Price in CHF
Teensy 3.2	https://www.pjrc.com/store/teensy32.html	CHF 34.00
Audio Shield (Rev C)	http://www.pjrc.com/store/teensy3_audio.html	CHF 14.25
Microphone	https://www.pjrc.com/store/microphone.html	CHF 1.25
Microphone Wind Protection	https://www.conrad.de/de/p/monacor-ws-20-mikrofon-windschutz-durchmesser-20-mm-1332972.html	CHF 3.60
Solar Power Management Module	https://www.maker-shop.ch/solar-power-manager-for-9v-12v-18v-solar-panel	CHF 49.90
Solar Panel	https://www.maker-shop.ch/polysilicon-solar-panel-18v-10w	CHF 19.90
Sensor Case PE	https://www.distrelec.ch/de/kunststoffgehaeuse-120x200x75mm-dunkelgrau-abs-ip65-rnd-components-rnd-455-00221/p/30064442?track=true&no-cache=true&marketingPopup=	CHF 11.50
Real Time Clock (RTC)	https://www.conrad.ch/de/p/euroquartz-quarzkristall-quarz-tc38-zyylinder-32-768-khz-12-5-pf-x-h-3-1-mm-x-8-mm-1-st-156098.html	CHF 0.95
LiPo Battery	https://www.distrelec.ch/de/lithium-polymer-akku-ah-mikroelektronika-mikroe-1120/p/30154716?track=true&no-cache=true&marketingPopup=false	CHF 16.50
Total		CHF 152.75

The correctness of the prices can not be guaranteed. Since the prices refer to the purchase price of spring 2022.

Figure 29: Frequency response of microphone (Projects Unlimited Inc., 2006)

Figure 30: Location of meteorological stations around the sensor
Retrieved at <https://s.geo.admin.ch/9b6d8ef3e5> (Date: 22 Nov. 2022).

Table 6: *Applied exponential function: $f(x) = a \cdot \exp(b \cdot x)$*

Frequency range [kHz]	a of exponential function	b of exponential function	R^2
0.05-1 kHz	4.58E-06	2.80E-01	0.950
1-2 kHz	1.43E-07	3.65E-01	0.950
2-3 kHz	2.52E-06	3.39E-01	0.945
3-4 kHz	3.17E-03	2.04E-01	0.944
4-5 kHz	3.01E-03	2.11E-01	0.904
5-6 kHz	1.64E-03	2.26E-01	0.899
6-7 kHz	4.69E-04	2.48E-01	0.900
7-8 kHz	2.86E-04	2.69E-01	0.906
8-9 kHz	4.36E-05	3.00E-01	0.905
9-10 kHz	3.17E-04	2.49E-01	0.910
10-11 kHz	1.04E-03	2.21E-01	0.900
11-12 kHz	1.71E-03	2.16E-01	0.889
12-13 kHz	1.04E-03	2.25E-01	0.892
13-14 kHz	1.26E-03	2.22E-01	0.895
14-15 kHz	1.19E-03	2.13E-01	0.880
15-16 kHz	6.19E-04	2.28E-01	0.881
16-17 kHz	2.92E-04	2.48E-01	0.895
17-18 kHz	1.37E-03	2.32E-01	0.886
18-19 kHz	3.11E-03	2.18E-01	0.850

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